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“BENEATH THE AROMA”

In every gathering, there is always a table prepared for everyone. Plates are arranged with care, food is served with a smile, and hands appear generous enough to feed the hungry. Yet not every meal offered comes from kindness. Some dishes are seasoned with control, plated with superiority, and served to remind people who owns the kitchen.

In kitchens, there are cooks who love being praised for the meals they serve, but quietly fear the day, others learn how to cook better. So, instead of teaching recipes, they keep hide them. They offer enough to satisfy hunger for a moment, but never enough for someone to prepare a feast on their own.

Like a table that is always full yet never shared equally, some forms of generosity are designed to create dependence rather than growth. Bread is given, but seeds are withheld. Soup is served, but no one is allowed near the stove. The guests remain grateful and satisfied, while the cook remains untouchable.

A passionate host understands that food is meaningful when everyone can contribute to the table. They teach others how to prepare ingredients, balance flavors, and create meals of their own. But those driven by insecurity prefer empty plates returning again and again, because dependence keeps them important.

This is why some people are welcomed only as long as they remain consumers and never creators. The moment someone begins experimenting with their own recipe, adding new flavors, or preparing something better than expected, criticism suddenly appears like bitter gourd in a dish. Small mistakes are overcooked, imperfections are magnified, and confidence is slowly starved.

Many kitchens appear warm from the outside, filled with inviting aromas and shiny tables, yet inside, the pantry is secured. Opportunities are rationed carefully. Knowledge is measured like high-end spices. Ambition is tolerated only when it stays smaller than the chef's own reputation and position.

But genuine generosity tastes different.

A sincere cook is not threatened when others learn beside them. They understand that a richer feast is created when more hands prepare the meal like unity occur. They do not hide ingredients to protect their pride, nor extinguish another's flame to keep attention on their own stove. Instead, they allow the table to grow wider, and welcomes new recipe's knowing that abundance is never diminished by sharing.

Food symbolizes comfort, survival, and community. Yet when generosity is used merely to maintain control, the meal feels cold. It may fill the stomach, but it still feels hunger.

And perhaps the saddest kitchen is not the one lacking food, but the one where people are never allowed to learn how to cook for themselves.

